

Title: Evaluation of the treatment outcome by an objective assessment with quantitative measurement of the magnitude of pain using electrical stimulation in fibromyalgia patients

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Abstract:

Fibromyalgia (FM) is a condition characterized by chronic and disabling pain. Since pain is commonly evaluated by a subjective assessment, it is difficult to evaluate the treatment effect objectively. In this report, the treatment outcome was evaluated by an objective assessment of pain in FM patients. Eight FM patients who fulfilled the American College of Rheumatology criteria for the classification of fibromyalgia participated. The severity of FM was assessed with the Japanese version of the Fibromyalgia Impact Questionnaire (JFIQ). The pain level was evaluated by pain degree, i.e., the magnitude of pain which was quantitatively measured with Pain Vision PS-2100™ and by visual analog scale (VAS). The treatment procedure involved the injection of a local anesthetic into bilateral lateral pterygoid muscles followed by the insertion of an oral device which restricted horizontal mandibular movements. In three cases, the treatment procedure was repeated and a clinical course was observed for 3-6 months. Pain degree and VAS were significantly reduced after the monotherapy. There was a significant correlation between pain degree and VAS. Pain degree, VAS and JFIQ were reduced in three cases in the follow-up period, although some fluctuations were observed. The pain relief procedure for lateral pterygoid muscles exhibited a significant effect on the reduction of systemic pain for temporomandibular disorder patients who fulfilled the classification criteria of FM, and could be considered as a treatment option for FM. It was also suggested that a quantitative measurement method for the magnitude of pain could be valuable for the evaluation of treatments for FM.

1. Introduction

Fibromyalgia (FM) is a disease characterized by systemic chronic pain. Because the major symptom, chronic pain, relies on subjective patient

evaluation, it is often difficult to determine the efficacy of treatments. Therefore, the development of objective evaluation methods is desired. Here, we report the evaluation of the effects of pain relief therapy targeting the lateral pterygoid muscle on FM symptoms in patients with TMD, using questionnaires and a quantitative pain measurement device.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Subjects: Eight female patients, aged 18 to 48 (mean 32 years), who met the American College of Rheumatology classification criteria for FM and concurrently had tenderness in the masticatory muscles (TMD), were investigated.

Table 1: Age, Sex, and Measurements of the Subjects

Patient ID	Age (years)	Sex	JFIQ
383	18	F	-
1401	32	F	84
3419	36	F	63
3420	41	F	87
3407	24	F	95
3403	24	F	100
3408	33	F	72
3405	48	F	63
Mean ± SD	32 ± 9.8	-	80 ± 15

2.2 Evaluation Methods: 1) Japanese version of the Fibromyalgia Impact Questionnaire (JFIQ). 2) Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain. 3) Quantitative electrical pain measurement device, Pain Vision PS-2100™ (Nipro, Osaka). This device measures the "pain degree" by comparing the threshold of electrical stimulation (minimum perceived current) with the current equivalent to the patient's pain. Pain degree = (Pain equivalent current - Minimum perceived current) / Minimum perceived current x 100.

2.3 Intervention: A local block was performed by injecting 0.9 ml of 2% xylocaine into the bilateral pterygomandibular space from the oral cavity. Simultaneously, an oral appliance was inserted to restrict horizontal mandibular movement and limit the contraction of the lateral pterygoid muscle.

Fig. 1: Pain relief therapy for the lateral pterygoid muscle. The arrow indicates the direction of approach to the lateral pterygoid muscle. For the purpose of illustration, the ascending ramus of the mandible and the zygomatic arch have been removed. First, the patient was instructed to relax and gently close their mouth to facilitate the relaxation of the masseter muscle. Next, using a 30-gauge, 16-mm dental needle, the insertion point was determined at the mucobuccal fold posterior to the molars from within the oral cavity. The needle

was advanced diagonally upward (as indicated by the arrow in the figure) to approximately half of its total length, and 0.9 ml of 2% xylocaine was injected.

2.4 Procedure: Measurements using JFIQ, Pain VAS, and Pain Vision were taken immediately before and after the procedure. For three cases (ID 3403, 3405, 3407), the treatment was continued, and the mid-term clinical course was followed.

3. Results

Following the procedure, both the pain degree and Pain VAS decreased significantly (Pain degree $P=0.008$, Pain VAS $P=0.016$). The reduction rate was greater for the pain degree (77.3%) than for Pain VAS (60.5%). (Fig.2) The pain-equivalent current decreased significantly ($P=0.008$), while the electrical stimulation threshold showed no significant change ($P=0.109$). (Fig3) In the clinical course of the three long-term cases, although there were occasional increases in pain degree, Pain VAS, and JFIQ scores, all cases showed an overall trend of improvement. At the final day of the observation period, all values had decreased compared to the initial visit.(fig.4-6)

Fig. 2: Pain Degree and Pain VAS

Fig. 3: Pain Vision Measurements

Fig.4

Fig.5

Fig.6

4. Discussion

Pain relief therapy for the lateral pterygoid muscle significantly reduced both Pain VAS and pain degree in a short period, demonstrating its effectiveness in suppressing FM pain. The mechanism by which a local procedure on the lateral pterygoid muscle suppresses systemic FM pain is considered to involve the central regulation of pain sensitivity. Afferent inputs from the lateral pterygoid muscle enter the mesencephalic trigeminal nucleus (Me5). Me5 has dense projections to the medullary dorsal reticular nucleus (DRt), which functions as a center for the descending pain facilitatory system. Therefore, the Me5-DRt system may be involved in the mechanism of systemic chronic pain suppression by the lateral pterygoid muscle block.

5. Conclusion

Pain relief therapy for the lateral pterygoid muscle was effective for systemic pain beyond the jaw region in patients with both FM and TMD. The quantitative measurement of absolute pain using electrical stimulation (Pain Vision) was highly useful in evaluating the improvement of pain before and after the procedure, enabling a chronological representation of FM pain severity.

Secondary Publication Statement: This article is an English translation of a secondary publication. The original article was peer-reviewed and published in Japanese in the journal *Clinical Rheumatology (Rinsho Rumachi)*, Vol. 21, pp. 249-255, 2009.